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The LUNZ Hub's RESPECT Project

The interdisciplinary Rapid Engagement with Stressed Peatland Environments and Communities in Transformation (RESPECT) project is affiliated with the Land Use for Net Zero, Nature and People (LUNZ) Hub and is funded by the UKRI Land Use for Net Zero programme. RESPECT aims to produce data, methods, landholder tools and proposals for governance reforms to change agricultural practices on peatland. RESPECT brings together researchers across Scotland and England with expertise in the natural and social sciences, humanities and law. RESPECT will also produce the Peatland Triage Tool (PTT), providing decision-support for landowners, land managers, farmers and crofters (collectively 'landholders') seeking to undertake peatland restoration. Upon completion, RESPECT will be able to provide a solid evidence base, and tools to inform land use decisions in relation to the restoration and sustainable management of agricultural peatlands.

This response was drafted with input from across our interdisciplinary RESPECT Team.

RESPECT response to draft Land use and Agriculture Just Transition Plan

This document provides a response from the RESPECT project to the Scottish Government's draft [Just Transition Plan for land use and agriculture](#). The fact that Scotland recognises changes in land use and agriculture to be both an environmental and a social challenge is incredibly important and reflects commitments at national level to statutory just transition principles, and outcomes. However, we are at a point now where principles and objectives need to be translated into action. This response offers critical reflections on the Plan's lack of integration with the forthcoming Fourth Land Use Strategy (LUS4) and the National Just Transition Outcomes, arguing that the Plan should be action-oriented, with concrete proposals, timelines, and responsibilities. The response highlights the need for systemic change, including stronger regulation of natural capital markets, inclusive land governance, and recognition of power imbalances in rural Scotland. The document stresses that a just transition must address procedural, distributive, and restorative justice, and include the voices and needs of underrepresented groups such as tenants, crofters, and future generations.

JUST TRANSITION VISION FOR 2045

Q1. The draft vision provides me with an understanding of the ambition of a just transition for land use and agriculture.

Mostly disagree

The draft Plan is lacking fundamental recognition of the overarching framework within which this sectoral plan will sit. Firstly, the overarching strategy for land use in Scotland is the forthcoming Fourth Land Use Strategy (LUS4). In our response to the [proposals for LUS4](#) we have urged for a stronger and more adaptive strategic approach for managing conflicting (and ever-changing) demands on Scotland's land. In this regard, we believe it is insufficient that the draft LUS4 is proposing to simply categorise existing or draft objectives from other policies and fill in some gaps. The purpose of the strategy should be to move beyond compartmentalisation and to *integrate* – not only at the landscape level, but at the level of national policymaking. It is the LUS4 that should set out the vision and objectives on how competing demands on land, and inevitable trade-offs, will be managed, keeping in mind that the capacity of the land to simultaneously deliver on all policy priorities may be restricted.

Secondly, where changes to the way land is used follow from this strategic prioritisation – and more so when changes are required to happen at the anticipated scale and speed – questions of justice come in. Scotland already has a framework for guiding the just transition. The [Climate Change \(Scotland\) Act 2009, s 35C](#) includes statutory just transition principles and Scottish Government’s [National Just Transition Planning Framework](#) lists the overarching just transition outcomes. More broadly, justice has been analysed and interpreted by (legal) scholars to include key elements such as distributive, procedural and restorative justice.

The proposed LAJTP *should* bring these frameworks together and set out *how* just processes and outcomes are going to be achieved for the transition towards “a net zero, nature-positive, wellbeing economy”/nation (proposed LUS4 vision). Whilst a level of interpretation of overarching objectives is helpful, the Plan should be *action oriented*. The document explicitly states that the Plan “will help integrate just transition into our activities and provide an understanding of how the people involved, impacted or benefiting from actions relating to land use and agriculture will be supported and empowered” – but fails to outline the actions that will do that. What is required are proposals for activities, with roles and responsibilities of different departments of Scottish Government to deliver the actions, timelines and milestones and KPIs, and required resources for delivery.

Lastly, the proposed vision itself does not recognise the heterogeneity of rural Scotland and the power imbalances within. From the perspective of procedural and distributive justice, it is not sufficiently clear whether current inequities in how decisions about land are made – relating to concentrated power – will have been addressed if the vision is realised. Special attention should be given to small-scale farmers, crofters and tenants – it is noted that no mention is made of tenant farmers which is not acceptable considering the specific challenges of this sector. The vision also places responsibility “to deliver improved and enduring benefits for their local communities, nature and climate” with the land use and agriculture sector and wider rural community. This should be a shared responsibility in recognition that land use transitions are delivered in rural areas, but contribute to national priorities (e.g., peatland restoration) and generate public value.

LONG-TERM OUTCOMES FOR 2045

Question 2: The outcomes for jobs, skills and economy provide an accurate description of what will be needed to achieve a just transition.

Mostly disagree

What is needed to achieve a just transition are concrete proposals for actions to deliver policy objectives that change the way land is used and farmed, in a manner that is fair and tackles inequality and injustice (see Scottish Government ‘[Just Transition: A Fairer, Greener Scotland](#)’ (2021)).

There needs to be much better integration between LUS4 and this sectoral Just Transition Plan, which is not the same as cross-referencing or copy-pasting key sections. The objectives for land use should be set out in a future LUS4 (Q1), and they should provide strategic direction on how trade-offs between different land use demands will be managed. The LAJTP should be a sub-set of the LUS4 which details how transitions in the land use and agricultural sectors will be managed in a *just* way, with concrete proposals. It is not a place for new objectives or more aspirational outcomes, but a place to *plan* for change with concrete actions and steps.

Terminologies also need to be streamlined – the LUS4 (which only covers 2026-2031) has copy-pasted longterm outcomes (for 2045) from this draft LAJTP but calls them example objectives. Objectives describe an intended aim or goal, whereas outcomes describe more concrete and measurable results. The chosen categories of objectives/outcomes between the LUS4 and the LAJTP are also different, and the LAJTP categories of outcomes are again different from the categories of National Just Transition Outcomes (Scottish Government, 2021). The Plan outlines “clear and joined up” communication as a key short-term objective for the sector. Yet, having all these overlapping strategic policies, with different structures and terminologies, with no clear hierarchy and, crucially, without concrete actions and timelines, is not contributing to this aim.

Lastly, we note that the last listed objective of a thriving natural capital sector that brings investment (even with the condition of community benefits) is particularly problematic from a just transition perspective in absence of a [robust regulatory system to ensure positive environmental and social impacts](#), and ensure access for all relevant interested parties including small-scale and tenanted farmers and crofters and communities (Q 11).

Question 3: The outcomes for environment and adaptation provide an accurate description of what will be needed to achieve a just transition.

Strongly disagree

We refer to our answers to Q1-Q2 in relation to some of the fundamental issues with the purpose and content of this Plan and why the overarching objectives for land use (change) should be set out in the LUS4, read together with Scottish Government's National Just Transition Outcomes. The LAJTP should focus on *how* those objectives and outcomes are relevant to and will be implemented in the land use and agriculture sectors, in an integrated and just way, through concrete proposals for actions.

The outcomes for environment and adaptation are lacking key elements of justice. Notably, in relation to peatlands, the first outcome ("There is support for people to integrate nature-based solutions into their businesses, such as [...] peatland restoration") fails to address key questions about *who* is able to make decisions about land and the integration of nature-based solutions (procedural justice), *who* bears the risks and reaps the benefits (distributive justice) and *how* does this address or exacerbate historic injustices (restorative justice). This is made worse by the fact that the Plan proposes to use "Hectares of restored peatland in Scotland per year" as an indicator of success. Whilst this may be easiest to measure, a focus on area-based targets in Scotland often prioritises (public and private support for) large-scale projects with simple governance structures (e.g., single owners) which can exacerbate existing inequalities in the way decisions about land are made and benefits are distributed – contrary to the goals of a just transition.

Question 4: The outcomes for communities and place provide an accurate description of what will be needed to achieve a just transition.

Mostly disagree

We refer to our answers to Q1-Q2 in relation to some of the fundamental issues with the purpose and content of this Plan and why the overarching objectives for land use (change) should be set out in the LUS4, read together with Scottish Government's National Just Transition Outcomes. The LAJTP should focus on *how* those objectives and outcomes are relevant to and will be implemented in the land use and agriculture sectors, in an integrated and just way, through concrete proposals for actions.

We agree that the outcomes reflect key aspects of a just transition in land use (change), relating to community recognition, involvement in land use decisions, and retention of wealth at local levels. However, we believe that this Plan needs to be action-oriented and should detail concrete, funded commitments to put ambitions into actions, particularly by strengthening inclusive governance of land. We also believe that distinctions between 'community and place' and 'people and equity' outcomes –differentiating between collective and individual needs – is not helpful as rural inequalities concern individuals as much as communities. We refer to the [National Just Transition Outcomes](#) which place 'citizens, communities and place' under one outcome.

Question 5: The outcomes for people and equity provide an accurate description of what will be needed to achieve a just transition.

Mostly disagree

We refer to our answers to Q1-Q2 in relation to some of the fundamental issues with the purpose and content of this Plan and why the overarching objectives for land use (change) should be set out in the LUS4, read together with Scottish Government's National Just Transition Outcomes. The LAJTP should focus on *how* those objectives and outcomes are relevant to and will be implemented in the land use and agriculture sectors, in an integrated and just way, through concrete proposals for actions.

We agree that the outcomes reflect key aspects of a just transition in land use (change), relating to participation of land users and tackling inequalities in land ownership and governance. Indeed, as we have argued in our response to the LUS4 consultation, land reform and collaborative land governance is not a separate issue from land use, but prerequisite for delivering a strategic approach to integrated land use in a fair and just way. However, we believe that this sectoral Just Transition Plan needs to be much more action-oriented and should detail concrete, funded commitments to put ambitions into actions, particularly by strengthening collaborative and inclusive governance of land. We also think that distinctions between 'community and place' and 'people and equity' outcomes – differentiating between collective and individual

needs – is not helpful as rural inequalities concern individuals as much as communities. We refer to the [National Just Transition Outcomes](#) which place ‘citizens, communities and place’ under one outcome.

SHORT-TERM OBJECTIVES/PRIORITY AREAS

Questions 6-10: Are these priority areas that need to be addressed?

Mostly disagree

The proposed short-term priorities around education, local focus, collaboration, innovation, equity, and communication are important but risk overemphasising individual and community responsibility while failing to address systemic barriers. Such barriers include Scotland’s concentrated land ownership, reliance on and imbalances in market powers, fragmented and restrictive policy and funding frameworks. Scotland’s objectives and targets for land use change are ambitious and demand action and reforms at scale and speed. However, without recognising and addressing systemic issues, the transition cannot be achieved in a fair and just way.

The listed short-term objectives seem to be largely shaped by actions that are already ongoing or in the pipeline, and that can (sometimes loosely) be linked to a just transition. Some links between action and the short-term objectives do not seem to be particularly strong, e.g., the Code of Practice for Sustainable and Regenerative Agriculture in relation to the objective on land-based education, knowledge, and skills systems. In other instances, current good practices are framed too narrowly, e.g., the Plan only explicitly considers land reform and governance with reference to the ongoing legislative process for the Land Reform Bill, without comprehensive recognition of evolving models of inclusive governance of natural resources more widely.

We need to take a step back from current approaches to critically evaluate (the impact of) current activities, as well as the barriers to delivering other activities that contribute to key policy priorities such as community wealth building. We then need to identify critical first steps that are necessary to deliver *transformative* change – towards “a net zero, nature-positive, wellbeing economy”/nation (proposed LUS4 vision) – in a just way. Ultimately, the short-term priorities should be explicitly linked to the objectives of the LUS4 for 2026-2031.

See Q11 on key priorities that are currently missing.

Question 11: Are there other short-term objectives that should be considered?

Yes

The LAJTP should include the following urgent *actions*:

- **Commitment to more political and financial support for LUS4**, which should provide clarity and strategic direction on how Scotland will manage trade-offs in decisions on land use (change), in light of the restricted capacity of the land (even when managed in an integrated way).
- **Robust regulation of private finance and natural capital markets.** The current over-reliance on unregulated markets to deliver public policy objectives is the single biggest risk to a just transition and is a major factor missing from strategic documents relating to land use (change) including this Plan and the proposed LUS4. [Voluntary carbon and nature markets require regulation](#) to ensure projects deliver genuine, lasting climate, ecological and social benefits and to detail legal responsibilities and liabilities for project delivery, especially in complex collaborations which require the setting up of new companies. Intergenerational justice is also an important factor due to the long-term nature of land use change/shifts in land use decision-making power through private investment, as contracts under the Peatland Code average 80 years.
- **Development of, and better support for, new adaptive governance mechanisms.** Such mechanisms must make land use (decisions) more inclusive of public and community voices, ensuring fairer distribution of benefits from land use change for current and future generations. In this regard, the piloted Regional Land Use Partnerships – and the South of Scotland Regional Land Use Framework – deserve much more attention and must be considered as entities capable of distributing funding, in accordance with previous advice from the [Scottish Land Commission](#) (2020).

Questions 12-19: Outcome indicators

We refer to our answers to Q1-Q2 in relation to some of the fundamental issues with the purpose and content of this Plan and why the overarching objectives for land use (change) should be set out in the LUS4, read together with Scottish Government's National Just Transition Outcomes. This means that we do not agree with the proposed structure of this LAJTP, which we believe should be action-oriented and include concrete proposals for activities and reforms that ensure that overarching land use objectives are delivered in a fair and just way, roles and responsibilities of different departments of Scottish Government to deliver the actions, timelines and milestones and KPIs, and required resources for delivery. This makes it difficult to respond to the questions about outcome indicators, as we do not believe new outcomes should be the focus of this Plan.

However, we make a few general observations in relation to the proposed indicators and a just transition:

- **Area-based indicators (such as for peatland restoration) are problematic from a just transition perspective**, as they can obscure crucial details about the quality of restoration, the delivery of multiple benefits including climate and biodiversity, and the *social* impacts at a local level. They risk prioritising 'simple' large-scale projects without addressing barriers to access public and private opportunities for investment in natural capital, including for crofters, tenants and small-scale farmers, exacerbate existing inequalities in the way decisions about land are made and benefits are distributed.
- **More thought needs to go into how impactful collaborative governance of land can be measured.** The Plan recognises the importance of more inclusive decision-making on land, yet its indicators reflect a narrow understanding. For example, they are focused on assets in community ownership, which is not a comprehensive measure of community power. Also, most community *assets* are buildings whereas what is lacking is an increase in the area of land under community control.
- **There need to be clearer connections between indicators and outcomes.** For example, the first outcome states: "Scotland's food production sector is productive and *sustainable*". However, the only indicator relating to the natural environment is on the value of natural capital, and this is not limited to the agricultural sector.

Question 20: Using a combination of indicators and anecdotal evidence could measure progress. Do you agree?

Transformative social change that underpins a just transition may sometimes be difficult to measure in quantitative terms and we agree that the use of, for example, case studies, stories of change, observational evidence, and evidence of institutional and legal reform, can be useful tools. However, what is important that systems for monitoring are robust and adequately supported by public funding.

Question 21: Are you aware of alternative evidence sources?

Transformative social change that underpins a just transition may sometimes be difficult to measure in quantitative terms and we agree that the use of, for example, case studies, stories of change, observational evidence, and evidence of institutional and legal reform, can be useful tools. However, what is important that systems for monitoring are robust and adequately supported by public funding.

Question 22: Are you aware of any ways in which the proposed outcomes and objectives need to take into account the different experiences of the following groups?

Yes

It is reiterated that we believe that this LAJTP should be action-oriented to implement overarching national land use (change) objectives (LUS4) and the National Just Transition Outcomes.

The LAJTP should intentionally address inequities in power and distribution of risks and benefits.

- **Young people:** As outlined above, the Plan needs to be more explicit on the risks of a focus on natural capital investment for a just transition. Notably, decisions made now on carbon projects can lock up land for 80+ years, so (governance) mechanisms are needed to represent the interests of current and future generations.
- **Groups at socio-economic disadvantage**, which could be interpreted to include tenants, crofters, and small farmers who face barriers in accessing natural capital finance, and who may be impacted by increased demand for land. In particular, the technical supporting document notes that the amount of rented agricultural land in Scotland is decreasing, but there is no mention of tenants in the Plan.

Question 23: Are you aware of any potential costs and burdens that you think may arise?

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